

Kinetics and Mechanisms of the Formation and Acid-catalysed Dissociation of β -Alaninatobis(ethylenediamine)-cobalt(III) Perchlorate

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Manuscript received 18 December 1992, revised 15 July 1993, accepted 14 October 1993

Kinetics and mechanisms of the formation of β -alaninatobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) complex ion by the reactions of *cis*-diaquabis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) ion and β -alanine have been carried out in aqueous solution having pH 3.8 to 7.03, $[\beta\text{-alanine}] = 0.02$ to 1.0 mol dm^{-3} , temperature 50 to 65° and $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4). Only the hydroxo-aqua form of the complex and non-ionic form of the ligand are reactive. The reaction involves concurrent reagent-dependent and reagent-independent paths. Investigation of the aquation reaction reveals that it proceeds through acid-dependent path only and follows a dissociative course of reaction.

Anation reactions of aqua-amine complexes usually proceed through ion-pair formation¹. However, their reactions with chelating ligands proceed through a two-step mechanism². In the present study, we have selected a chelating ligand, the β -alanine, which has different donor atoms at two ends. This work has been undertaken as an extension of our earlier studies on the formation of mixed chelate complexes with ligands having two different donor atoms at two ends³. In order to make the study complete, we have also carried out the acid-catalysed dissociation of the formed complex β -alaninatobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) ion and reported the same in the following pages.

Results and Discussion

Spectra, stoichiometry of the reactions and reaction products : The spectra of the *cis*-diaqua complex, *cis*- $\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{3+}$ (Fig. 1, curve VII, λ_{max} 495 nm, $\epsilon_{\text{max}} 65 \pm 2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the β -alaninato complex, $\text{Coen}_2(\beta\text{-alan})^{2+}$ (curve-VI, λ_{max} 495 nm, $\epsilon_{\text{max}} 106 \pm 3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are given in Fig. 1. The formation of the title complex was identified by matching the spectrum of the product (curve V) with that of a known solution of the β -alaninato complex. The product

Fig 1 Spectral scanning of the reaction between *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ with β -alanine; $[\text{Complex}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\beta\text{-alalH}] = 4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (I) 0 min, (II) 1 h, (III) 3 h, (IV) 1 day, (V) 3 days, (VI) $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{B-alal})]^{2+}$, (VII) $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$.

of the aquation reaction was also identified by spectral matching with a known solution of the *cis*-diaqua complex.

Determination of pK_1 and pK_2 of *cis*-

$\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{3+}$: The acid dissociation constant values of the diaqua complex were determined at 55° by the pH-titration technique : $\text{p}K_1 = 5.24 \pm 0.07$ and $\text{p}K_2 = 7.94 \pm 0.06$. The $\text{p}K$ value of β -alanine is 9.87 (55°) as given in the literature⁴.

Formation of $\text{Coen}_2(\beta\text{-alan})^{2+}$: Rate measurements could not be made at pH's above 7.03 as above this pH, the insoluble complex hydroxide separates out slowly. The rate constants were determined at 55° at a particular concentration of the ligand β -alanine but with variation of pH from 3.0 to 7.03. All the rate measurements uniformly show simple first order plot and the rate constants determined from these plots are given in Table 1. In the experimental pH range the complex and the ligand exist in various protonated and deprotonated forms. However, as the rate measurements could not be made beyond pH ~ 7.03, involvement of the deprotonated form of the ligand, β -alan and dihydroxo form of the complex in the reaction, is ruled out. Similarly as there is no reaction below pH ~ 3.0, the diaqua form of the complex ion also does not take part in the reaction. The k_{obs} versus pH plot also indicates in the same direction. So ultimately we are left with the hydroxo aqua form of the complex $\text{Coen}_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{2+}$ and protonated form of the ligand β -alanine that takes part in the reaction.

At a particular pH of the reaction mixture, concentration of the hydroxo aqua form is given by (1)

$$[\text{Co(en)}_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+} = \frac{K_1[\text{H}^+][\text{Co}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}}{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2} \quad (1)$$

where $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}$ denotes total concentration of the cobalt complex and K_1 and K_2 are acid dissociation constant values of the diaqua complex.

The rate law for the reaction may be given as (2),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{d[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_1[\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2} [\text{Co}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\beta\text{-alaH}]_{\text{T}} \\ \text{or } \frac{d[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}}{dt} &\cdot \frac{1}{[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\beta\text{-alaH}]_{\text{T}}} = \\ k_{\text{obs}} &= \frac{K_1k[\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2} \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

In the above rate equation, k is the rate constant for the reaction of hydroxo aqua complex and β -alanine. $[\beta\text{-alaH}]$ stands for total β -alanine concentration. Plot of $k_{\text{obs}} x$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$, where $x = ([\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2)$ is linear having no intercept on $k_{\text{obs}} x$ axis (Fig. 2). From the slope of this plot, k was evaluated by the least-square method as $(10.0 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-4} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 55°, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Table 2 incorporates the rate data for the formation of the complex $[\text{Coen}_2(\beta\text{-alal})]^{2+}$ at pH 5.0 with different amounts of β -alanine between 50 and 65°. These plots are all linear and do not indicate a limiting

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING pH ON RATE OF FORMATION OF β -ALANINATOBIS(ETHYLENEDIAMINE)COBALT(III)^a ION

pH	$10^7[\text{H}^+]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})^b$	$10^{16} k_{\text{obs}} x^c$
3.8	1584	1.6	160
4.0	1000	3.8	4018
4.14	724	6.9	3914
4.42	380	13.4	2228
4.54	288	15.3	1522.5
4.75	178	22.5	943.3
4.94	115	30.52	605.6
5.00	100	34.53	544
5.30	50	51.99	280
5.50	31.6	62.6	176.7
5.80	15.8	76.6	89.2
6.17	6.8	92.0	41
6.31	4.90	96.0	29.9
6.80	1.58	186.0	18.6
7.03	0.93	284.0	17.3

^a $[\text{complex}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; temp = 55°.

^b k_{obs} values are pseudo-first order rate constants at $[\beta\text{-alal}]_{\text{total}}$.
^c $x = [\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2$.

 Fig. 2. Plot of $k_{\text{obs}} x$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$.

value for the highest concentration of the ligand studied. Ion-pair formation does not play a role in this reaction. From the slopes and intercepts of k_{obs} versus $[\beta\text{-alanine}]$ plot (Fig. 3) as obtained by the least-squares analysis of data, reagent-free

 Fig. 3. Plots of k_{obs} vs $[\beta\text{-alanine}]$, $[\text{Complex}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm $^{-3}$, $I = 1.0$ mol dm $^{-3}$, pH = 5.00, temp = 55°.

and reagent-dependent paths (k_1 and k_2) were evaluated (Table 2) along with the corresponding activation parameters. The reactions taking place at this stage may then be given as

Reagent-free path :

Reagent-dependent path :

Reactions (4a) and (5) indicate formation of monodentate β -alanine complex.

The anation reaction takes place in a single slow rate-determining step without showing any slow ring closing step. Similar fast ring closing steps have been observed in the anation of $\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}$ with oxalic acid and oxalate ion in acidic aqueous solution¹. The enthalpies of the reaction (Table 2) are low by cobalt(III) standard. At this stage it is difficult to say whether the reaction is associative or dissociative in nature, but it is likely that the reaction involves some associative character. An associative interchange mechanism has been confirmed for the oxalate/oxalic acid anation of diaquabis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) by pressure studies⁵.

 TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[\beta\text{-ALANINATE}]$ ON THE RATE OF COMPLEX FORMATION AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

$10^2 [\beta\text{-alal}]$ mol dm $^{-3}$	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$			
	50°	55°	60°	65°
1		3.40		
2	3.00	3.45	4.22	
7		3.81	5.17	
10	2.72	3.95	5.62	6.63
15		4.47	6.20	7.31
20	3.15	4.80	6.83	8.18
40	4.0	6.20	9.07	11.00
60	4.82	7.75	11.73	
100	6.50	11.00		
$k_1 (10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$	2.54 ± 0.17	3.26 ± 0.15	4.24 ± 0.14	5.64 ± 0.23
$k_2 (10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$	3.86 ± 0.13	7.64 ± 0.04	12.47 ± 0.13	14.45 ± 0.14
$\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 13 \pm 1.8 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$		$\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 16 \pm 1.1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$		$\Delta S_1^\ddagger = -35 \pm 5 \text{ cal mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
				$\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -24 \pm 7 \text{ cal mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$

Aquation of $\text{Coen}_2(\beta\text{-alal})^{2+}$: Aquation of the complex ion $\text{Coen}_2(\beta\text{-alal})^{2+}$ was investigated in perchloric acid, sodium perchlorate medium between 50 and 65° at $I = 1.0$ mol dm $^{-3}$. The rate constants were evaluated by simple first order plot which shows good linearity for 2–3 half-lives.

All the rate constants obtained with various amounts of acids are given in Table 3. Plots of rate constants versus $[HClO_4]$ are all linear having zero intercept on the rate axis. Second order rate constant (k_3) as obtained from these plots by a linear least-squares method are also given in Table 3.

TABLE 3-RATE DATA FOR ACID CATALYSED DISSOCIATION OF β -ALANINATOBIS(ETHYLENEDIAMINE)-COBALT(III) COMPLEX AT DIFFERENT ACIDITIES AND TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	$10^4 k_{obs} (s^{-1})$ at $[HClO_4] (mol\ dm^{-3})$				$10^4 k_3\ dm^3\ mol^{-1}\ s^{-1}$
	0.2	0.5	0.7	1.0	
50	0.25	1.00	1.45	1.97	2.15 ± 0.10
55	0.62	1.70	2.25	3.05	3.02 ± 0.25
60	0.75	2.32	3.24	4.30	4.44 ± 0.20
65	1.25	2.70	4.00	5.75	5.67 ± 0.15

$\Delta H^\ddagger = 16.0 \pm 1.5\ kcal\ mol^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -20 \pm 4\ e.u.$

On the basis of the reaction products and first order dependence of rate on $[H^+]$, the mechanism of aquation may be represented by equation (7),

On the basis of the mechanism given in equation (7) the rate of dissociation of the complex may be represented by equation (8),

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Rate} &= k' [\text{conjugate acid}] = k' K_3 [\text{complex}][H^+] \\
 &= k_3 [\text{complex}] [H^+] \quad (8)
 \end{aligned}$$

where k_3 is the second order rate constant, K_3 the equilibrium constant for the formation of the protonated species (conjugate acid, CA) and k' is the rate constant for the rate-determining step. K_3 is assumed to be very small, so that $[I] \gg [II]$.

β -Alanine forms a six-membered pseudo-aromatic chelate ring. Protonation of the chelate

ring, by way of its inductive effect, weakens the metal-ligand bonds with ultimate rupture of one of them. As soon as one-ended dissociation of the chelate takes place, it loses its pseudo-aromaticity, leading to destabilisation of the chelate. It may reasonably be conjectured that as soon as one end of the β -alanine moiety detaches from the complex, the other end also dissociates immediately. This might explain the behaviour of acid-catalysed dissociation of β -alanine chelate ring. Which end of the chelate ring (N or O) ruptures initially is difficult to say. However, in cobalt(III) complexes monodentate β -alanine ligand is linked through its nitrogen end⁶. So, it is likely that the oxygen end of the chelate ring ruptures first.

From all the foregoing observations, it may be concluded that the present aquation reaction primarily follows a dissociative path.

Finally, some explanation is necessary regarding the stereochemistry of all reactions. In aqueous solution all the reacting complex species exist in *cis-trans* equilibrium, and at 25° *trans* \rightarrow *cis* conversion rate for the hydroxo-aqua complex is four times greater than *cis* \rightarrow *trans* conversion rate⁷. A chelate ring formation is possible only with the *cis*-structure. So in our opinion it is only the *cis*-form that is involved in the present reaction without being influenced by any *cis* to *trans* conversion rate. Again, for the aquation reaction it is only the *cis*-diaqua form (in the experimental acidity range only the diaqua form can exist) that takes part in the reaction as *cis* \rightarrow *trans* conversion rate is very very slow in comparison to *trans* \rightarrow *cis* conversion rate⁸.

Experimental

β -Alaninatobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III)perchlorate : It was prepared from carbonate perchlorate complex as described earlier⁹. β -Alaninato complex was prepared by digesting equimolar amounts of the carbonato complex and β -alanine together for 30 min in perchloric acid medium (pH ~ 4.0). Pink crystals of the desired

complex which settled at the bottom of the reaction vessel were recrystallised from aqueous solution and dried in air (Found : Co, 12.84; N, 14.88; C, 17.91; H 4.91. $\text{Coen}_2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ calcd. for : Co, 12.66; N, 15.02; C, 18.02; H, 4.72).

cis-Diaquabis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III)perchlorate : It was prepared in situ whenever required by acidifying the corresponding carbonato complex in solution with perchloric acid.

All other reagents used were of AnalaR grade. The pH and ionic strength (I) of the solutions were adjusted by adding appropriate amount of the respective acid or salt (NaClO_4). A Systronics digital pH-meter was used for the purpose.

Measurement of acid dissociation constants for the complex $\text{cis-}[\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ at 55° : The acid-dissociation constants (K_1 and K_2) of the diaqua complex were determined by equilibrating a solution containing requisite amounts of the diaqua complex and sodium perchlorate at 55° and titrating the mixture with standard sodium hydroxide. The mathematical equation involved in this procedure is given by the equation,

$$\frac{\bar{h}}{2-\bar{h}}[\text{H}^+]^2 = \frac{1-\bar{h}}{2-\bar{h}}[\text{H}^+]K_1 + K_1K_2 \quad (9)$$

where, $\bar{h} = [\text{Na}^+] / [\text{complex}]_{\text{Total}}$ and $[\text{H}^+] =$

hydrogen ion concentration, obtained from observed pH, K_1 and K_2 are first and second acid dissociation constants. A plot of $\frac{\bar{h}}{2-\bar{h}} [\text{H}^+]^2$ against $\frac{1-\bar{h}}{2-\bar{h}} [\text{H}^+]$ gives slope equal to K_1 and intercept $K_1 K_2$. The values of K_1 and K_2 were derived from these data.

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